

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Adding and Updating Assets in NIH BioArt Source

Overview of the process of adding and updating Human reference Atlas images in BioArt Source

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Introduction

Two-dimensional digital objects from the Human Reference Atlas (HRA) are held in NIH BioArt Source (National Institute of Health 2025), a free science and biomedical art resource library, where they can be accessed and used by other researchers and general audiences. This increases the reach of the Human Reference Atlas (HRA) and helps ensure that HRA assets will be supported after funding ends.

The HRA collection in BioArt Source is revised and expanded every six months as part of the HRA release process. This SOP documents how to update HRA digital objects in NIH BioArt Source so that the repository contains the latest published versions. The primary audience for this SOP is the HRA Integrator who updates HRA digital objects in BioArt Source, but the SOP may also be of interest for people wishing to use these digital objects or users interested in uploading their own images to NIH BioArt Source.

Roles and Responsibilities

The **Center Assistant** maintains usernames and passwords for CNS access to NIH BioArt Source.

The **HRA Integrator** is responsible for updating and editing the HRA Collection in NIH BioArt Source each time there is an HRA release, typically every six months.

The **HRA Lead** is responsible for reviewing and approving the release of uploaded HRA digital objects.

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
Center Assistant	Traci Smith	cnsctr@iu.edu

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HRA Integrator	Hrishikesh Mulkutkar	infoccf@iu.edu
HRA Lead	Katy Börner	katy@iu.edu

Procedures

NIH BioArt Source is an open-source collection of more than 2,000 science and medical art visual assets created by professional illustrators, hosted by the National Institutes of Health. Illustrations of functional tissue units (FTUs) developed for the Human Reference Atlas are available via this portal. The HRA collection is hosted at <https://bioart.niaid.nih.gov/discover?collection=2>.

Asset collections are updated every six months, following each release of the Human Reference Atlas.

Logging in and accessing HRA collections

- Obtain the login credentials from the Center Assistant.
- Log in to the BioArt website at <https://bioart.niaid.nih.gov/sign-in>.
- Once logged in, search for HRA in the search bar at the top of the page, as shown in **Fig. 1**.

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Figure 1. Navigating to the HRA collection in BioArt.

Updating and editing assets in BioArt Source

- Click on the asset you want to edit or delete. Update any file that was revised in the recent HRA release.
- New digital objects included in the latest release can be updated by clicking on the Submit button in the toolbar of the portal to add files under organ illustration.
- Update metadata as necessary, using the HRA Knowledge Graph as the source of truth. The files can be found at <https://lod.humanatlas.io/2d-ftu>.
- Review current release notes to identify revised 2D FTUs.

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The screenshot shows the NIH BioArt Source interface for a 'Renal Corpuscle' entry. At the top, there is a search bar and navigation links for 'Submit', 'Discover', and 'FAQs'. Below the search bar, there are 'Edit' and 'Delete' buttons. The main content area features a detailed anatomical diagram of a renal corpuscle with various cell types labeled: Afferent arteriole endothelial cell, Macula densa epithelial cell, Efferent arteriole endothelial cell, Glomerular mesangial cell, Glomerular visceral epithelial cell, Parietal epithelial cell, Epithelial cell proximal tubule, and Glomerular capillary endothelial cell. A 50 µm scale bar is present. To the right of the diagram, there is a metadata section for 'BIOART-000562' with 124 views and 117 downloads, a Creative Commons BY license, and a category of 'Anatomy, Cells and Organelles'. A 'Description' box contains text about the functional tissue unit (FTU) illustration. Below this is a 'Representation' section with a 'Download' button and a QR code. A 'Cite This Entry' section provides the citation: 'Human Reference Atlas. (12/18/2024). Renal Corpuscle. NIAID NIH BioArt Source. bioart.niaid.nih.gov/bioart/562'.

Figure 2. Updating assets in BioArt Source.

- Click on the Edit button. The menu shown in **Fig. 2** should appear.

The screenshot shows the 'Submit Files' interface in BioArt Source. At the top, there are three steps: '1 Create New Group', '2 Enter Details', and '3 Submit'. A 'Next' button is visible. Below the steps, there is a note: 'Note: * indicates a required field.' The main area is divided into two sections. On the left, there is a 'Discover Thumbnail' section with a thumbnail image of the renal corpuscle. Below the thumbnail, there is a 'Caption*' field with the text 'Renal Corpuscle' and a note: 'Provide a short description of this image (max 255 characters)'. Below the caption, there is a 'Color Group' section with a grid of colored circles. Below the color group, there is a 'Files*' section with a list of files: '2d-ftu-kidney-renal-capsule.ai', '2d-ftu-kidney-renal-capsule.png', '2d-ftu-kidney-renal-capsule.svg', and 'thumb_2d-ftu-kidney-renal-capsule-01.jpg'. At the bottom of the files list, there are '+ Add to File Group' and 'Remove File Group' buttons. On the right, there is a large dashed box with a plus sign and the text 'Add New File Group'.

Figure 3. Submitting files to BioArt Source

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- To upload a revised image click on the “Add to the File Group” button on the left side of the screen.
- All the digitals assets are located in this folder: `101224_FTU_thumbnails`.
- Upload all file formats.
- Check 2D data and metadata for correctness and completeness.

Adding new assets

- Review current release notes to identify new 2D FTUs.
- Upload new FTU digital objects by clicking on the Submission button in the toolbar of the portal.
- Select Add new file group and select all following files: .PNG, .AI, .SVG and .JPG, which is used for thumbnail images.
- Give a suitable caption and click the Next button.
 - Update metadata as necessary, using the HRA Knowledge Graph as the source of truth. The files can be found at <https://lod.humanatlas.io/2d-ftu>.
 - Tag Anatomy and Cell Organelles in Category
 - Update Keywords entry with FTU name.

Figure 4. Click on the Submit button to publish your submission

- To upload a revised image click on the “Add to the File Group” button on the left side of the screen.
- All the digitals assets are located in this folder: `101224_FTU_thumbnails`.
- Upload all file formats.
- Check 2D data and metadata for correctness and completeness.

References and Resources

National Institute of Health. 2025. “NIH BioArt Source.” <https://bioart.niaid.nih.gov/>.

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Glossary

3D reference object: Polygon mesh of 3D spatial objects (e.g., anatomical structures), their object node hierarchy, materials, and surface color and texture. They are created by medical illustrators with the involvement of subject matter experts following standard operating procedures.

functional tissue unit (FTU): A functional tissue unit is the smallest tissue organization, i.e., a set of cells, that performs a unique physiologic function and is replicated multiple times in a whole organ. FTUs can be hierarchically nested.

Human Reference Atlas (HRA): The Human Reference Atlas is a comprehensive, high-resolution, three-dimensional, multiscale atlas of all the cells in the healthy human body. The Human Reference Atlas provides standard terminologies and data structures for describing specimens, biological structures, and spatial positions linked to existing ontologies.

Acknowledgments

The Human Reference Atlas (HRA) is under active development by the Indiana University Mapping Component as part of the HuBMAP HIVE, SenNet CODCC, KPMP, and GUDMAP efforts with expert input by the HRA Editorial Board and in close collaboration with experts from more than 25 other consortia. Data was provided by HuBMAP and other Tissue Mapping Centers. This research has been supported by the NIH Common Fund through the Office of Strategic Coordination/Office of the NIH Director under awards OT2OD033756 and OT2OD026671, by the Cellular Senescence Network (SenNet) Consortium through the Consortium Organization and Data Coordinating Center (CODCC) under award number U24CA268108, and by the NIDDK under awards U24DK135157 and U01DK133090. The work has also been supported by the Kidney Precision Medicine Project grant U2CDK114886, and the NIH National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID), Department of Health and Human Services under BCBB Support Services Contract HHSN316201300006W/HHSN27200002, as well as the American Dental Association Science and Research Institute and the Canadian Institute for Advanced Research's MacMillan Multiscale Human program. The content is solely the responsibility of the authors and does not necessarily represent the official views of the National Institutes of Health.